

Enhanced Terahertz Spectroscopy of a Monolayer Transition Metal Dichalcogenide

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2D materials, including transition metal dichalcogenides, are attractive for a variety of applications in electronics as well as photonics and have recently been envisioned as an appealing platform for phonon polaritonics. However, their direct characterization in the terahertz spectral region, of interest for retrieving, e.g., their phonon response, represents a major challenge, due to the limited sensitivity of typical terahertz spectroscopic tools and the weak interaction of such long-wavelength radiation with sub-nanometer systems. In this work, by exploiting an *ad-hoc* engineered metallic surface enabling a ten-thousand-fold local absorption boost, enhanced terahertz spectroscopy of a monolayer transition metal dichalcogenide (tungsten diselenide) is performed and its dipole-active phonon resonance features are extracted. In addition, these data are used to obtain the monolayer effective permittivity around its phonon resonance. Via the direct terahertz characterization of the phonon response of such 2D systems, this method opens the path to the rational design of phonon polariton devices exploiting monolayer transition metal dichalcogenides.

growing field that provides versatile solutions for applications requiring manipulation and control of long wavelength light (encompassing the mid- infrared (IR) and terahertz (THz) ranges).^[1] This is typically realized in bulk materials that support the emergence of surface phonon polaritons (PhPs) in the spectral region – known as the Reststrahlen band – between their transversal optical (TO) and longitudinal optical (LO) phonon modes. Compared to plasmon polaritons, PhPs feature lower intrinsic loss and better light confinement for long wavelengths.^[2] They have thus been proposed for a variety of applications in IR and THz photonics, e.g., in surface-enhanced IR absorption spectroscopy,^[3] heat management,^[4] radiative cooling,^[5] imaging and sensing.^[6]

In this context, 2D materials are becoming game changers that enable PhP responses from atomically thin layers.^[2b,7] For

1. Introduction

Phonon polaritonics, dealing with the hybridization of lattice vibrations with electromagnetic radiation, has become a rapidly

example, it has been shown that PhPs in 2D multilayered van der Waals materials such as hexagonal boron nitride (hBN)^[8] and α -phase molybdenum trioxide (α -MoO₃)^[9] can exhibit a natural hyperbolic dispersion (related to the anisotropy in the sign of the principal permittivity components), which in turn makes it possible to achieve unique functionalities like nanoscale directional energy transfer and subdiffractional focusing. Single layers of 2D materials can further push PhP confinement to its ultimate limits, as it has been observed in monolayer hBN,^[10] where the PhP wavelength can be hundreds of times smaller than that of light of the same frequency in free space.

An interesting class of 2D material systems is represented by transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs). Thanks to their semiconducting properties, TMDs have the potential to be employed in next-generation high-performance, low-power-consumption electronic and computing technologies.^[11] Furthermore, TMDs exhibit a direct bandgap in their monolayer form and host tightly bound excitons that are stable even at room temperature, which makes them appealing for optoelectronic applications.^[12] TMDs also possess the attractive advantage of gate-tunable optical properties, which is not available in insulating platforms like hBN.

For what concerns long-wavelength photonics, semiconducting TMDs hold promise in relation to their distinctive

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characteristics, for example regarding hyperbolic PhPs,^[1,2b,13] chiral phonons,^[14] and potential for ultraslow polariton interactions.^[2b] Indeed, although slow-moving PhPs in TMDs are not ideal for propagation-related (e.g., waveguiding) applications, such low-velocity modes are expected to have long lifetimes, guaranteeing an extensively prolonged energy exchange with, e.g., interacting molecules, which can benefit strong light-matter coupling experiments.^[2b]

As a member of the semiconducting TMD family, tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) is considered a promising platform for electronics as well as optoelectronics,^[15] and has recently shown long-range ferromagnetic order at room temperature when doped with vanadium,^[16] thus providing interesting opportunities also for spintronics. Optical phonons play an important role in all these applications, as they are involved in strong electron-phonon scattering processes in TMDs,^[17] which can ultimately limit device performance.

Despite such a significant interest, dipole-active phonon modes of monolayer TMDs are so far explored only via first-principles calculations or indirectly, e.g., via Raman characterization, due to evident difficulties in performing direct spectroscopic measurements on such ultra-thin material systems in their PhP regions (i.e., in the THz range). This also implies that a reliable estimation of their dielectric permittivities at such frequencies, essential for the design of PhP devices, is still unavailable.^[1] In this work, by exploiting a nano-engineered metallic surface featuring properly-shaped nanoslot resonators as a platform for enhanced THz spectroscopy, we successfully characterized the THz response of monolayer WSe₂ in the spectral region of its E' optical phonon mode. By fitting the experimental data with the results of electromagnetic simulations, we were able to estimate the E' phonon resonance frequency, lifetime, and group velocity, as well as extract the effective permittivity of monolayer WSe₂ in the THz range. Our method can be directly extended to other monolayer TMDs and, more broadly, to other 2D material platforms, for the THz characterization of their optical phonon response and the advanced design of 2D THz PhP devices.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Design, Fabrication, and THz Characterization of X-Shaped Nanoslot Array

Resonant nanoantennas are well-known for their ability to locally enhance the interaction of light with vibrational modes, thereby improving the sensitivity of direct absorption spectroscopy in traditional far-field measurement setups.^[18] To perform enhanced THz spectroscopy of the targeted TMD monolayer, we designed a substrate featuring resonant metallic nanostructures to boost the local THz electric field, in analogy with the strategy we previously exploited to characterize^[18c] (or manipulate^[19]) the phonon response of semiconducting nanocrystals. While in our former studies, rod-like nanoantennas were employed, our new design makes use of a resonant nanoslot geometry (nanoslots are apertures with nanoscale features on a metallic surface^[20]), to provide better mechanical support to the 2D material. Resonant nanoslots typically present an area at their center where the local electric field is enhanced (see Figure S1, Supporting Infor-

mation). However, the enhancement factor in this area can be relatively weak. To improve such enhancement and, at the same time, preserve a robust mechanical support that avoids excessive stretching and bending of the 2D material, we adopted a heuristic approach that exploited the tapering of the nanoslots while limiting the size of the apertures.

Recently, we have shown that tapering of rod-like THz nanoantennas reduces the Ohmic loss of such resonators, thus improving their electric field localization properties.^[21] This technique is also effective for “negative” structures such as the nanoslots considered here. In this case, a straightforward geometry to better confine the electric field at the nanoslot center is represented by a bowtie-shaped slot (i.e., a structure tapered at the two extremities) with an extended nanogap area. Our final design eventually takes on a characteristic X shape (Figure 1) that allows us to further enhance the electric field in the nanogap and, at the same time, limit the size of the individual apertures composing the structure (for a comparison among a uniform rectangular nanoslot, two examples of bowtie nanoslots, and the X-shaped nanoslot, see Figure S1, Supporting Information).

Figure 1a shows a sketch of the investigated array of X-shaped nanoslots prepared in a 100-nm-thick gold layer on a silicon substrate, highlighting its key design characteristics. For the array to have a local field resonance in the proximity of the targeted E' phonon mode of monolayer WSe₂, which is located at ≈7.5 THz (as estimated by previous first-principles studies and Raman measurements),^[22] the X-shaped structure features a gap in its center of w (500 nm) \times g (50 nm) along the x and y directions, respectively, while the four arms of the X shape have a height $h = 2.2$ μm along the y direction (see additional geometrical details of the X shape in the bottom right panel of Figure 1a). The array periodicity in the x and y directions is set to $s_x = s_y = 5.4$ μm in a square lattice geometry.

The designed array was fabricated using electron-beam lithography and covers an area of 2.5×2.5 mm² (for fabrication details, see Experimental Section). Figure 1b,c shows scanning-electron-microscope (SEM) images of the fabricated X-shaped nanoslot array (for a close-up zoom of the nanogap area, see also Figure S2, Supporting Information). To characterize the THz response of the fabricated structure, we used a Fourier transform spectrometer in a transmission configuration (see THz characterization details in Experimental Section). The measured transmission spectrum of the bare array is shown in Figure 1e (gray curve), highlighting a far-field resonance position at ≈7.3 THz.

All numerical simulations for the sample design were performed using COMSOL Multiphysics. In addition, after the THz characterization of the fabricated device, we employed the Nelder-Mead optimization method incorporated in the COMSOL numerical solver to best fit the measured array transmission (see details in Experimental Section). To this purpose, the permittivity of gold in the THz range was described via the Drude equation: $\epsilon_D(\nu) = 1 - \nu_p^2 / (\nu^2 + i\gamma_D\nu)$, where ν is the frequency, $\nu_p = 2080$ THz the plasma frequency of gold taken from literature,^[23] while γ_D is the damping factor, which we used as the key fitting parameter in the simulations. The result of the fitting procedure is shown in Figure 1e (red curve), returning a value for the damping factor $\gamma_D = 449$ THz. The simple adjustment of the damping

Figure 1. X-shaped nanoslot array: design, fabrication, and THz characterization. a) Schematic of the X-shaped nanoslot array on a silicon substrate. Relevant parameters: $s_x = s_y = 5.4 \mu\text{m}$; $t = 100 \text{ nm}$; $h = 2.2 \mu\text{m}$; $w = 500 \text{ nm}$; $g = 50 \text{ nm}$; $d = 100 \text{ nm}$; $\theta_1 = 20^\circ$; $\theta_2 = 40^\circ$. b) Scanning electron microscope (SEM) image of the fabricated array. c) A zoomed-in SEM image ($5.4 \times 5.4 \mu\text{m}^2$) of a single nanoslot. d) Spatial distribution of the electric field enhancement on a plane 0.65 nm above the metallic surface, at the frequency of 7.5 THz . E_0 is the electric field amplitude of the incident THz light, while E is the local electric field amplitude. e) Measured (gray curve) and simulated (red curve) transmission spectra of the X-shaped nanoslots array (the incident THz light is polarized along the y -axis). Inset: Electric field enhancement of the X-shaped nanoslots as a function of frequency, numerically estimated at the nanogap center on a plane 0.65 nm above the metallic surface (which corresponds to the thickness value of monolayer WSe_2 ^[34]).

value allows us to obtain an excellent agreement between the experimental transmission spectrum of the nanoslot array in the THz range and the simulated one, which will be instrumental in properly extracting the permittivity of monolayer WSe_2 (see below).

Numerical simulations also enable the visualization of the electric field right above the X-shaped nanoslot, where the 2D material will be located. Such local field is highly concentrated in the nanogap region (see Figure 1d), and its resonance is well aligned to the targeted dipole-active phonon mode of monolayer WSe_2 at 7.5 THz , with a peak enhancement value estimated to be $|E|/|E_0| \approx 100$ at the gap center, as shown in the inset of Figure 1e. Further details regarding the electric field distribution along the z -axis, tunability of the resonance, and polarization dependence of the X-shaped nanoslot array are reported in Figures S3–S5 (Supporting Information).

2.2. Phonon Response of Monolayer WSe_2 : First-Principles Calculations, Raman Spectroscopy, and Direct THz Characterization

Phonons in monolayer WSe_2 can be investigated through first-principles calculations.^[22,24] Using this approach, we computed its phonon dispersion by means of the calculation package Quantum Espresso (see configurations in the Experimental Section),^[25] which incorporates, among others, methods such as density functional theory (DFT)^[26] and density functional perturbation theory (DFPT).^[27] Figure 2a shows the result of this calculation, while Figure 2b illustrates the atomic displacement of two characteristic phonon modes in the monolayer (the out-of-plane Raman-active A_1' mode and the in-plane E' mode, which is both dipole- and Raman-active) and their connection with the phonon modes of bulk WSe_2 . Examining the phonon dispersion

Figure 2. Phonon modes in monolayer WSe₂. a) Calculated phonon dispersion of monolayer WSe₂. b) Schematic of atomic displacements for the optical phonon modes A₁' and E' of monolayer WSe₂ and their bulk mode counterparts. Notation: Raman-active (R), dipole-active (D), both Raman and dipole inactive (Silent).

in Figure 2a, we can first notice the absence of LO-TO splitting at the Γ point for the E' mode (located at ≈ 7.5 THz, i.e., ≈ 250 cm⁻¹), a distinctive feature of 2D polar materials (such as the TMDs) in their monolayer form.^[28] We can also see that the A₁' mode closely approaches the E' mode at the Γ point. The close spectral proximity between these two modes (i.e., E' and A₁') is characteristic of monolayer WSe₂, while in multilayer systems the respective modes tend to progressively separate in frequency when increasing the number of layers.^[29]

In our experiments, we employed a monolayer WSe₂ (2Dsemi-conductors Inc.) prepared via chemical vapor deposition (CVD) and then transferred on the X-shaped nanoslot array. Figure 3a shows an optical image of the sample, where it is possible to identify the array at the center of the gold-coated silicon chip, as well as the WSe₂ layer (darker area) that fully covers the nanoslots (see

also the zoom-in picture in the right panel of Figure 3a). Monolayer WSe₂ exhibits a direct bandgap with a peak photoluminescence (PL) emission at ≈ 1.65 eV, while from monolayer to multilayer the bandgap becomes indirect and narrows (with PL peak at 1.54 eV for the bilayer, 1.46 eV for the trilayer).^[30] PL can thus be used to identify the number of WSe₂ layers. In this regard, we performed PL emission spectroscopy on our sample at different locations over the array, by employing a 445-nm laser excitation. As the seven measurements reported in Figure 3b show, the PL spectra of the CVD-grown WSe₂ transferred over the X-shaped nanoslot array are consistently peaked at ≈ 1.65 eV, confirming the monolayer nature of the employed TMD over the area of interest.

To experimentally identify the spectral location of the E' mode of the monolayer WSe₂ covering our sensing chip, we performed micro-Raman spectroscopy measurements, exploiting the fact that this mode is also Raman active. Since, as mentioned earlier, the E' and A₁' modes almost overlap in monolayer WSe₂, we employed polarized Raman spectroscopy, given that the A₁' mode dominates the Raman response in a parallel-polarization configuration (i.e., a configuration in which the scattered light is collected via a polarizer with orientation parallel to the input laser polarization) but is almost forbidden in crossed polarization, while the E' mode contributes nearly equivalently in both cases.^[29b,31] This can be quantitatively seen via the calculation of the Raman activity in the two configurations (Figure 4a). 99.7% and 57.1% of Raman activity of the A₁' and E' modes are found in the parallel-polarization configuration (blue curve), respectively. As a result, the E' mode, with its 42.9% residual activity, is dominant in the cross-polarization configuration (red curve) with a negligible A₁' contribution (see also the isolated contributions and amplitudes of the two modes for the two polarization configurations in Figure S6, Supporting Information). Figure 4b presents the example of a polarized Raman spectroscopy measurement taken at a nanoslot location (laser excitation: 473 nm, power: 5.91 mW, focal spot size: 0.6 μ m, acquisition time: 700 s), which results to be in good agreement with the calculation outcomes (Figure 4a) for what concerns the WSe₂ Raman peak locations (for additional unpolarized Raman measurements and related comments, see Figure S7, Supporting Information). This investigation thus confirms the spectral location of the E' phonon mode for our sample (≈ 250 cm⁻¹, i.e., ≈ 7.5 THz), which is the target of our THz characterization study.

Figure 5 (gray curve) shows the THz transmission measurement performed on the X-shaped nanoslot array covered with the monolayer WSe₂. As can be seen, a spectral dip (which can be referred to as a Fano-like resonance^[32]) forms on the array response at ≈ 7.5 THz (i.e., in the spectral position of the WSe₂ E' mode). This behavior is typical of nanoantenna-enhanced vibrational spectroscopy measurements^[18c,32] and results from the coupling between the resonant mode of the employed sensing nanostructures and the targeted vibrational mode. Our technique is thus capable of retrieving the dipole-active phonon spectral signature of monolayer WSe₂ by means of the field enhancement delivered by the nanoslots, providing evidence of direct far-field THz phonon spectroscopy of an atomically thin material. Making use of this measurement, we can finally extract an effective permittivity for the investigated monolayer WSe₂ and also evaluate

Figure 3. Sample image and photoluminescence measurements. a) Optical image of the X-shaped nanoslot sample covered with monolayer WSe_2 (darker area in the left panel). b) Photoluminescence spectra of the WSe_2 layer, taken at seven different points over the surface of the X-shaped nanoslot array. Curves are shifted vertically for clarity.

its key phonon resonance features, as detailed in the following section.

2.3. Permittivity Extraction

As recent literature has shown, even in the absence of LO-TO splitting, monolayers of polar materials support a strongly confined PhP mode that corresponds to the 2D LO phonon.^[10b,28,33] In particular, ref. [28] introduced the convenient idea of utilizing, for compatibility with standard numerical tools, a “bulkified” medium (with thickness l equal to the monolayer thickness) to reproduce the monolayer response in electromagnetic simulations. The effective in-plane permittivity of such medium (its out-of-plane permittivity is taken as equal to 1) can be written as:

$$\epsilon_{\text{eff}}(\nu) = 1 + \frac{4\epsilon_{\text{env}}\nu_0 u_g}{l(\nu_0^2 - \nu^2 - i\nu\tau^{-1})} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_{env} is the permittivity of the surrounding medium and u_g , ν_0 , and τ are the LO phonon group velocity, resonance frequency,

and lifetime, respectively. Using this model, we were able to employ numerical simulations to best fit the experimental transmission spectrum of Figure 5 (red curve, see details in Experimental Section), in a manner analogous to what was previously done for the bare array transmission. In the simulations, the layer thickness was set to $l = 0.65$ nm, considering the reported interlayer spacing value for WSe_2 ,^[34] while $\epsilon_{\text{env}} = 1$, taking into account that the monolayer is effectively suspended in air in the hot spot regions of the nanoslot array (i.e., the nanogap areas), where spectroscopy is enhanced (see Figure S8, Supporting Information). Through the fitting procedure, we independently retrieved the values of the LO phonon frequency, lifetime, and group velocity, which are respectively associated with the spectral position, linewidth, and relative transmission change of the Fano-like resonance feature observed in the experimental data (Figure 5). We thus obtained $\nu_0 = 7.47$ THz, in good agreement with the results of both first-principles calculations and Raman measurements, a long phonon lifetime $\tau = 5.56$ ps, and an ultraslow group velocity $u_g = 610$ m s^{-1} . Regarding the latter quantity, such experimentally estimated value of the phonon group velocity at the

Figure 4. Polarized Raman response of monolayer WSe_2 . a) First-principles calculation of the Raman activity of monolayer WSe_2 for a parallel (blue curve) or crossed (red curve) polarization configuration. A Gaussian broadening of 2 cm^{-1} is used for visualization purposes. b) Experimental polarized Raman spectra of the WSe_2 layer, taken at an X-shaped nanoslot gap area by employing a parallel (blue curve) or crossed (red curve) polarization configuration.

Figure 5. Enhanced THz spectroscopy of monolayer WSe₂. Measured transmission spectrum of the X-shaped nanoslot array covered with monolayer WSe₂ (gray curve). The red curve is the simulated transmission spectrum obtained via the numerical fitting of the experimental data, by varying the permittivity of monolayer WSe₂. Inset: Zoomed-in plot showing the actual fitting range.

Γ point gives valuable insight into the small-wavevector dispersion of 2D LO phonons in WSe₂ and is found to be fairly aligned with previously reported theoretical calculations (1600 m s⁻¹^[35]). **Figure 6a,b** shows the dispersion of the real and imaginary part of the effective permittivity and refractive index of monolayer WSe₂, as extracted from our experiments. Making use of these data in electromagnetic simulations, we can estimate the visibility enhancement of the phonon spectral signature of monolayer WSe₂ when placed on the X-shaped nanoslot array. **Figure 6c** shows the transmission spectra with (darker color curves) and without (lighter color curves) monolayer WSe₂, in the case in which silicon is directly used as a substrate (simulated blue curves), or when the nanoslot array is employed (red curves: simulation; gray curves: experiment). For comparison purposes, all curves are normalized to the transmission of a bare silicon substrate (see further details on how these curves are obtained in Experimental Section). As can be seen, the overall experimental transmission of the nanoslot array is $\approx 50\%$ of the simulated one. This reduction in transmission is due to the fact that, owing to fabrication constraints, the patterned nanoslot area in the gold film (see **Figure 1a**) is smaller than the illuminating THz beam in our experiment, whereas in the simulations an infinitely extended array is considered through periodic boundary conditions (the origin of the reduced transmission was confirmed via the measurement of a gold-coated silicon sample with a square aperture of the same size as the X-shaped nanoslot array, i.e., 2.5×2.5 mm² – see **Figure S9**, Supporting Information). By calculating the transmission difference ΔT without and with monolayer WSe₂, we can directly compare the visibility of the E' phonon resonance in the various cases presented in **Figure 6c**. **Figure 6d** shows that ΔT is extremely small ($< 0.1\%$) when monolayer WSe₂ is placed directly on a silicon substrate (blue curve). Conversely, it increases by ≈ 10 times in the simulations when using the X-shaped nanoslot

array (red curve). Solely due to the limited size of the fabricated array, the experimental visibility enhancement is instead ≈ 5 (see gray curve), a value that nonetheless allows the phonon resonance peak to emerge from the noise floor of our measurement. The origin of the visibility enhancement is closely linked to the increased THz absorption of WSe₂ in the nanogaps of the X-shaped nanoslots. **Figure 6e** shows the simulated THz absorption density evaluated at a point in the center of the nanoslot gap at half the thickness of the WSe₂ layer (red curve), as well as the same quantity for a WSe₂ layer directly placed on silicon (blue curve). A significant 10^4 increase in the local absorption of WSe₂ is found in the nanogaps, which results in an overall absorption boost of a factor of ≈ 19 in monolayer WSe₂ when placed on the X-shaped nanoslot array compared with the case of a bare silicon substrate (see simulation presented in **Figure S10**, Supporting Information). The locally intensified radiation-matter interaction is key to enabling the direct observation of the phonon spectral signature of such an atomically thin material in the THz range.

3. Conclusion

We have performed direct THz spectroscopy of monolayer WSe₂ around its E' optical phonon mode, by exploiting the local field enhancement of an *ad-hoc* designed array of X-shaped nanoslots. Such resonant nanostructures have enabled a 10^4 boost in the local THz absorption of the TMD material, resulting in a fivefold increase (tenfold theoretical) in the visibility of its phonon spectral signature. This has allowed us to retrieve the effective permittivity of monolayer WSe₂ in the range 5–10 THz, as well as its key optical phonon characteristics, i.e., the phonon resonance frequency $\nu_0 = 7.47$ THz, lifetime $\tau = 5.56$ ps, and group velocity at the Γ point $u_g = 610$ m s⁻¹. Such long phonon lifetime and slow group velocity highlight the possibility of exploiting PhPs in this 2D material platform for, e.g., nanolocalized sensing, strong radiation-matter interactions, or the exploration of forbidden transitions in the THz range.^[36]

Our strategy can be straightforwardly applied to other monolayer TMDs as well as different 2D materials. It can also enable the investigation of few-layer heterostructures, to explore the tailoring of the THz optical phonon response in these artificially created stacks. Furthermore, inverse design^[37] can be used to define the sensing substrate geometry for an optimized spectroscopic enhancement. While in this study a CVD-grown monolayer was employed, our method can also be extended to the characterization of mechanically exfoliated samples, making use of recently developed techniques for i) the exfoliation of large-area flakes (mm-size and beyond),^[38] which are directly compatible with measurements on THz resonator arrays, or ii) the selective excitation of individual metallic resonators in the THz range,^[39] which could be exploited to sense flakes of more typical (micrometric) size. Such an extensive range of opportunities for the extraction of the THz optical properties of 2D materials thus promises to open up unprecedented pathways for the design of ultrathin PhP devices operating in the THz spectral region.

4. Experimental Section

Electromagnetic Simulations and Fittings: Electromagnetic simulations were performed using COMSOL Multiphysics,^[40] exploiting the Optics

Figure 6. Effective permittivity of monolayer WSe_2 , phonon resonance visibility, and local absorption enhancement. a) Effective permittivity of monolayer WSe_2 , as extracted via the procedure described in the text (real part: green curve; imaginary part: magenta curve). b) Corresponding refractive index. c) Relative transmission with (darker color curves) and without (lighter color curves) monolayer WSe_2 for the case of a silicon substrate (simulated blue curves) and the X-shaped nanoslot array (X-NS – red curves: simulation; gray curves: experiment); simulated curves are estimated using the permittivity shown in (a). The scale of the right axis (referring to the silicon substrate case) is expanded by a factor of 5 compared to that of the left axis, for comparison purposes. d) Transmission difference without and with monolayer WSe_2 (a quantity used to estimate the phonon peak visibility), for the three cases reported in (c). e) Simulated THz absorption density evaluated at a point in the middle of the WSe_2 layer, when the latter is positioned on silicon (blue curve) or over the nanogap of an X-shaped nanoslot (red curve); the input electric field of the incident light in the simulation is $E_0 = 1 \text{ V m}^{-1}$.

Module and the Optimization Module. In simulations, a lattice of X-shaped gold nanoslots was placed on a silicon substrate. The top air and bottom silicon domains were truncated by two perfectly matched layers to avoid any spurious reflections. Along the x - and y -directions, two pairs of Floquet periodic boundary conditions were used to simulate an infinitely large array. The refractive index of silicon was set to 3.42. The permittivities of gold and WSe_2 in the THz range were described via the models detailed in the main text. Regarding the illumination condition, light with y -axis polarized electric field from the air domain was employed to excite the nanoslots. Using COMSOL finite-element-method solver in the frequency domain, near- and far-field quantities could be obtained, such as the local electric field enhancement, absorption, and scattering cross-sections,

as well as the integral average of the power flow for calculating the array reflection and transmission.

For the numerical fittings, the Nelder-Mead optimization method incorporated in the numerical solver was used to fit the measured transmission curves. In the case of the bare X-shaped nanoslot array, the objective function was defined as $f_{\text{obj}} = \sum_{\nu=5 \text{ THz}}^{10 \text{ THz}} |T_{\text{sim}}(\nu, \gamma_D) - a_0 \cdot T_{\text{exp}}(\nu)|$, in which a_0 is a normalization parameter, γ_D is the damping factor in the Drude equation describing the permittivity of gold, and $T_{\text{sim/exp}}$ is the simulated or measured relative transmission spectrum (calculated as the transmission ratio of the nanoslot array sample to a reference silicon substrate). a_0 and γ_D were set as the fitting parameters to search for the minimum of f_{obj} in the range 5–10 THz. The fitting procedure, performed

exploiting the Béluga cluster of the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, returned the values $a_0 = 2.1486$ and $\gamma_D = 449$ THz. In the case of the array covered with monolayer WSe₂, the objective function was defined as $f'_{\text{obj}} = \sum_{\nu=7.2}^{7.64} |T'_{\text{sim}}(\nu, \nu_0, u_g, \tau) - a_1 \cdot T'_{\text{exp}}(\nu)|$, in which a_1 is the normalization parameter, ν_0 , u_g , and τ are the LO phonon resonance frequency, group velocity, and lifetime, respectively, in the effective permittivity of monolayer WSe₂ (Equation 1), and $T'_{\text{sim/exp}}$ is the simulated or measured relative transmission spectrum of the nanoslot array covered with monolayer WSe₂. The fitting parameters to minimize f'_{obj} were a_1 , ν_0 , u_g , and τ . Since the phonon mode feature is located in a relatively narrow region around 7.5 THz, the fitting range was limited to 7.2–7.64 THz, to reduce the computational heaviness of the procedure. The following values were retrieved: $a_1 = 2.0851$, $\nu_0 = 7.474$ THz, $u_g = 610$ m s⁻¹, and $\tau = 5.56$ ps. Note that the normalization parameters a_0 and a_1 allow us to take into account the fact that, in our experiments, the patterned nanoslot array area in the gold film is smaller than the illuminating THz beam. The slight difference between a_0 and a_1 can be attributed to the non-perfectly identical alignment of the array with respect to the larger THz beam in the two measurements, before and after the transfer of monolayer WSe₂. These parameters were used to appropriately compare the experimental relative transmission spectra of the X-shaped nanoslots with and without monolayer WSe₂ (gray curves in Figure 6c), which were plotted as $T'_{\text{exp}}(\nu)$ and $(a_0/a_1) \cdot T'_{\text{exp}}(\nu)$, respectively. The simulated spectra shown as red curves in the same figure correspond to $T'_{\text{sim}}(\nu)$ and $T_{\text{sim}}(\nu)$.

Fabrication of the X-Shaped Nanoslot Array: A high-resistivity silicon wafer (10 k Ω -cm) was cut into 10×10 mm² samples. Such samples were then cleaned in acetone, isopropyl alcohol (IPA), and water in an ultrasonic bath (60 s for each substance) and finally treated in oxygen plasma. The silicon substrate was covered with a 5-nm-thick chrome adhesion layer and a 100-nm-thick gold film via electron beam physical vapor deposition using a Kenosistec KE500ET system. The sample was then spin-coated with an electron beam resist (polymethyl methacrylate-PMMA-A4) at 1800 rpm for 60 s. Later, the substrate was baked on a hotplate at 180 degrees Celsius for 420 s. The lithographic step was performed by using a Raith 150-two electron beam lithography system, and an array area of 2.5×2.5 mm² was patterned with the X-shaped nanoslot design. The PMMA layer was then developed in a solution of Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)/IPA (1:3) for 30 s at 4 degrees Celsius and stopped in IPA for 20 s. The patterned PMMA layer was used as a mask for the dry etching process, which was conducted in a SENTECH SI500 plasma-enhanced reactive ion etching system. The process was performed with 40 sccm of Ar gas flow at -5 degrees Celsius, with a reactor pressure of 1 Pa and a RF generator power of 60 W. The process was divided into two consecutive steps of ≈ 100 s each, to maintain the temperature around -5 degrees Celsius (the exact etching time was determined through scanning electron microscopy inspection of the sample after each step). Finally, the PMMA was removed in hot acetone, a procedure followed by an oxygen plasma treatment.

Terahertz Measurements: THz transmission spectroscopy was carried out using a Fourier Transform Spectrometer (FTS, Blue Sky Spectroscopy Inc.) equipped with a Si₃N₄ blackbody source. A pyroelectric detector (QMC Instruments Ltd.) was employed to collect the transmitted THz radiation during the interferogram scans. The samples with dimensions of 10×10 mm² were mounted on a motorized rotation stage, which was then installed inside the FTS chamber. To remove water vapor-related absorption lines in the measurements, the FTS chamber was vacuum-pumped for 1 h until it reached a pressure value below 100 mTorr. THz transmission spectra were retrieved from an average of 1000 interferograms acquired with a nominal resolution of 0.15 cm⁻¹. Before Fourier transforming the interferogram traces, Kaiser-Bessel-derived windows^[41] were used to remove from such data echo peaks intrinsic to the spectrometer configuration as well as resulting from Fabry-Pérot reflections associated with the silicon substrate (see Figure S11, Supporting Information for more details).

Raman and Photoluminescence Spectroscopy: The CVD-grown WSe₂ transferred on the nanoslot array was characterized by Raman spectroscopy using a Horiba system (iHR320) equipped with a confocal BX-41 Olympus microscope, a linearly polarized diode-pumped continuous-wave solid-state laser (TEM 00 DPSS laser) (04-01 Cobolt) with a 473 nm

wavelength, and a back-illuminated deep depleted charge-coupled device. The double polarized measurements were acquired using a half wave-plate (polarizer) and a Glan-Thomson prism (analyzer, extinction ratio 100 000:1). The laser power was set at 5.91 and 13.9 mW, respectively, for the polarized and unpolarized Raman measurements (Figure S7, Supporting Information). The focal spot size was 0.6 μ m, and the acquisition time was 700 s for all Raman measurements. The photoluminescence spectra of monolayer WSe₂ were obtained with a laser excitation wavelength of 445 nm and a laser power of 160 mW.

Density-Functional-Theory Calculations: The phonon dispersion of monolayer WSe₂ was computed using the density functional theory software package Quantum Espresso.^[25] The generalized gradient approximation (GGA) of the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange-correlation functional^[42] was employed. The ultrasoft pseudopotentials^[43] of tungsten and selenium used in the calculation are available on materialscloud.org. The kinetic energy and density cutoffs were set at 80 and 960 Ry, respectively. The 2D material domain cutoff method was used to truncate the calculation domain.^[44] Hubbard correction was implemented using DFPT.^[45] Brillouin zone integration was performed using a $12 \times 12 \times 1$ Monkhorst-Pack grid. The atomic structure was relaxed with forces on the atoms < 0.0001 eV \AA^{-1} . The Raman activity of monolayer WSe₂ was calculated using Quantum Espresso with the incorporated local-density approximation (LDA). The pseudopotentials of tungsten and selenium used in the Raman calculation were generated by the code of the Optimized Norm-Conserving Vanderbilt Pseudopotential (ONCVSPSP),^[46] available on pseudo-dojo.org.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

X.J. and V.A. contributed equally to this work. L.R. conceived the study and supervised its realization. X.J. designed the nanoslot array and performed the electromagnetic simulations. V.A. and A.T. set up the fabrication of the nanoslot array. X.J., Y.-G.J., and L.R. contributed to the THz measurements, as well as their analysis and interpretation. X.J. performed the first-principles calculations concerning the phonon response of monolayer WSe₂ with the computational resources provided by P.B. A.P., L.S., E.O., and A.R. contributed to the photoluminescence and Raman measurements and their analysis and interpretation. M.S. and Y.J. were involved in designing the experiments and collecting the relevant literature.

X.J., V.A., and L.R. prepared the first version of the manuscript. All the authors discussed the theoretical and experimental results and helped with the redaction of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

2D materials, permittivity extraction, phonon response, surface-enhanced spectroscopy, terahertz radiation

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